

First evidence for a virtual ^{18}B ground state

A. Spyrou^{a,b,*}, T. Baumann^a, D. Bazin^a, G. Blanchon^c, A. Bonaccorso^d, E. Breitbach^e, J. Brown^f, G. Christian^{a,b}, A. DeLine^g, P.A. DeYoung^h, J.E. Finck^g, N. Frankⁱ, S. Mosby^{a,b}, W.A. Peters^j, A. Russel^g, A. Schiller^k, M.J. Strongman^{a,b}, M. Thoennessen^{a,b}

^a National Superconducting Cyclotron Laboratory, Michigan State University, East Lansing, MI 48824, USA

^b Department of Physics & Astronomy, Michigan State University, East Lansing, MI 48824, USA

^c CEA, DAM, DIF F-91297 Arpajon, France

^d Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Sez. di Pisa, Largo Pontecorvo 3, 56127 Pisa, Italy

^e Department of Physics, Marquette University, Milwaukee, WI 53201, USA

^f Department of Physics, Wabash College, Crawfordsville, IN 47933, USA

^g Department of Physics, Central Michigan University, Mt. Pleasant, MI 48859, USA

^h Department of Physics, Hope College, Holland, MI 49423, USA

ⁱ Department of Physics & Astronomy, Augustana College, Rock Island, IL 61201, USA

^j Department of Physics & Astronomy, Rutgers University, Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA

^k Department of Physics & Astronomy, Ohio University, Athens, OH 45701, USA

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ABSTRACT

The decay of the neutron unbound ground state of ^{18}B was studied for the first time through a single-proton knockout reaction from a 62 MeV/u ^{19}C beam. The decay energy spectrum was reconstructed from coincidence measurements between the emitted neutron and the ^{17}B fragment using the MoNA/Sweeper setup. An *s*-wave line shape was used to describe the experimental spectrum resulting in an upper limit for the scattering length of -50 fm which corresponds to a decay energy <10 keV. Observing an *s*-wave decay of ^{18}B provides an experimental verification that the ground state of ^{19}C includes a large *s*-wave component. The presence of this *s*-wave component shows that *s*-*d* mixing is still present in ^{18}B and that the $s_{1/2}$ orbital has not moved significantly below the $d_{5/2}$ orbital.

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The understanding of nuclear structure in the vicinity of the drip lines has been one of the main goals of both experimental and theoretical studies of exotic nuclei during the past two decades. Among the observed structural features is the two-neutron halo, which is found in some extremely neutron rich light nuclei [1]. The two-neutron halo nuclei also exhibit a “Borromean” property [2], which refers to bound three-body systems with their two-body components (*n*-*n*, *n*-core) unbound. Some well-known examples of Borromean nuclei are ^6He , ^{11}Li , ^{14}Be , and ^{17}B [3]. For the description of such systems, an understanding of the interaction of the two-body subsystems, in particular the *n*-core interaction, is essential [4].

A Borromean nucleus which has been identified as a two-neutron halo candidate [1,5] is ^{19}B . Ozawa et al. [5] indicated that

^{19}B might be a two-neutron halo nucleus, based on the one- and two-neutron separation energies from the 1995 Atomic Mass Evaluation [6]. Suzuki et al. [7] measured the ^{19}B interaction cross section, σ_I , and showed that the effective root-mean-square radius ($\bar{r}_m = 3.11 \pm 0.13$ fm) is consistent with a two-neutron halo structure. However, in the same publication a description of ^{19}B as a ^{15}B -core with four neutrons outside the core, similar to the structure of ^8He (α -core plus four neutrons [8]), was also proposed. In addition, ^{19}B was explored as a candidate for exhibiting Efimov states [9]. These excited states are expected near and below the three-body breakup threshold in systems with large spatial dimensions, possibly of the order of 100 fm [1,10]. As shown by Mazumdar et al. [9], Efimov states would be expected in ^{19}B only if the unbound subsystem ^{18}B (*n*- ^{17}B) would have a virtual ground state corresponding to a scattering length of a few hundred fm.

Although the structure of ^{18}B plays a significant role in the understanding of ^{19}B , it has not been studied extensively. ^{18}B was first shown to be neutron-unbound in 1984 in an ^{56}Fe fragmentation experiment [11]. This observation was also confirmed a year

* Corresponding author at: National Superconducting Cyclotron Laboratory, Michigan State University, East Lansing, MI 48824, USA.

E-mail address: spyrou@nsl.msu.edu (A. Spyrou).

later through the fragmentation of ^{40}Ar [12]. At the same time, Poppelier et al. [13] presented a calculation of the structure of ^{18}B . They predicted a 4^- ground state for ^{18}B from the coupling between $\pi(p_{3/2})$ protons and $\nu(d_{5/2})$ neutrons. However, later shell model calculations by Warburton and Brown [14] predicted a 2^- ground state with a 4^- first excited state at 450 keV.

The ground state configuration of ^{18}B is not obvious since the evolution of the sd -shell orbitals along the $N = 13$ isotone chain results in s - d mixing and could even lead to an inversion between the $s_{1/2}$ and $d_{5/2}$ orbitals for the lighter isotones. Although the large $s_{1/2}$ - $d_{5/2}$ gap in ^{22}O [15] does not persist in its $N = 13$ neighbor (^{21}O), the $d_{5/2}$ orbital in ^{21}O is still about 1.2 MeV lower than the $s_{1/2}$ which makes the ground state configuration dominated by $\nu(d_{5/2})^5$ [16,17]. A similar behavior is expected for ^{20}N where the $\nu(d_{5/2})^{-1}$ is coupled to the $\pi(p_{1/2})^1$ resulting in a 2^- ground state and a 3^- low-lying excited state. Although the experimental data is not adequate to determine the gap between the $s_{1/2}$ and the $d_{5/2}$ orbitals, shell model calculations show that the ground state configuration for ^{20}N is similar to ^{21}O [18].

The first evidence for sd mixing in the $N = 13$ isotones appears in ^{19}C . Although its ground state configuration has been under debate for a long time ([19,20] and references therein), there is now strong theoretical and experimental evidence that the dominant neutron component is $(d_{5/2})^4 \otimes (s_{1/2})^1$ resulting in a $1/2^+$ ground state [21–24]. The first two low lying excited states are predicted to be $5/2^+$ and $3/2^+$ although the order is not clear from the experimental results [25,26]. These excited states correspond to a mixture of three neutron configurations, namely $(d_{5/2})^5$, $(d_{5/2})^3 \otimes (s_{1/2})^2$ and $(d_{5/2})^4 \otimes (s_{1/2})^1$ [25]. The strong admixtures in the states of ^{19}C are a result of the evolution of the sd shell where the $s_{1/2}$ and $d_{5/2}$ orbitals become degenerate. Therefore, one would expect that in ^{18}B , which has one less proton than ^{19}C , the $s_{1/2}$ and the $d_{5/2}$ orbitals might be inverted. Since ^{18}B is unbound with respect to neutron emission, such an inversion would be reflected in the neutron decay of its ground state.

In the present work we report on the measurement of the decay energy of ^{18}B . The neutron separation energy of ^{18}B was estimated in the latest Atomic Mass Evaluation [27] to be -480 keV. Theoretical calculations [14,28–30] do predict that ^{18}B is unbound with respect to neutron emission, however the estimated neutron separation energy varies from a few hundred keV up to 2.5 MeV. In this work ^{18}B was populated through a single-proton knockout reaction from a ^{19}C beam. The decay energy spectrum of ^{18}B was reconstructed event-by-event from the four-momentum vectors of the decay products, ^{17}B and n . This invariant-mass spectroscopy technique has been used successfully in the past for the study of unbound systems at the neutron drip line up to oxygen [31].

The experiment was performed at the National Superconducting Cyclotron Laboratory (NSCL) at Michigan State University. The ^{19}C secondary beam was produced by the fragmentation of a 120 MeV/u ^{22}Ne primary beam in a 2139 mg/cm 2 thick Be target. The A1900 fragment separator [32], utilizing a 1050 mg/cm 2 Al achromatic degrader located at its intermediate focal plane, was used for the isotopic selection of ^{19}C at 62 MeV/u. The total secondary beam intensity was 250 pps, of which 25% corresponded to ^{19}C and 75% to ^{17}B which could be separated in the analysis by time-of-flight. After passing through two Cathode Readout Drift Chambers (CRDCs) for tracking purposes, the secondary beam interacted with a 470 mg/cm 2 Be reaction target. Downstream from the target, the charged reaction products were deflected by the large-gap superconducting dipole magnet (Sweeper) [33] and were detected by a series of position and energy sensitive detectors. The emitted neutrons were detected around 0° by the Modular Neutron Array (MoNA) [34]. Details of the experimental setup can be found in Ref. [35].

Fig. 1. a) Particle identification, b) Neutron time-of-flight without fragment gates, c) Neutron time-of-flight in coincidence with the ^{19}C beam, d) Neutron time-of-flight in coincidence with the ^{17}B fragments.

The identification of the fragment of interest, ^{17}B , is presented in Fig. 1. The interaction of the ^{19}C beam with the Be reaction target resulted in several different fragments including ^{17}B . Fig. 1a shows the particle identification using the energy loss of the fragments in a thin (5 mm) plastic scintillator and the time-of-flight (ToF) between the target and the thin scintillator.

The particle identification includes the ^{19}C beam, the fragment of interest ^{17}B , and additional light fragments that correspond to $N = 2Z$ which fall within the acceptances of the setup. The events shown in Fig. 1a are in coincidence with events in MoNA that fall within the dotted lines in the neutron time-of-flight spectrum (Fig. 1b). The events within the marked gate include real neutron events as well as a background coming mainly from cosmic ray muons. To illustrate the effect of the random background Fig. 1c shows the neutron ToF spectrum gated on the ^{19}C events from Fig. 1a. The same spectrum corresponding to coincidences with the ^{17}B fragments is shown in Fig. 1d. As expected, the ^{19}C beam is in coincidence with random background while events in MoNA which are in coincidence with the ^{17}B fragments correspond to real neutron events.

The decay energy of ^{18}B was determined through invariant mass spectroscopy using Eq. (1).

$$E_d = E_{18\text{B}} - M_f - M_n \quad (1)$$

where M_n and M_f are the masses of the neutron and the fragment (here ^{17}B), respectively, and

$$E_{18\text{B}}^2 = M_f^2 + M_n^2 + 2(E_n E_f - p_n p_f \cos(\theta_{\text{open}})). \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), $E_{n,f}$ and $p_{n,f}$ are the energy and momentum of the neutron and the fragment and $\cos(\theta_{\text{open}})$ is the opening angle between them.

The experimentally determined decay energy spectrum depends on the properties of the decay itself and also the characteristics of the experimental setup (i.e. target thickness, detector resolutions, and geometrical acceptances). For this reason, the MoNA/Sweeper setup was simulated in a Monte Carlo calculation, which included the geometry of the setup, the reaction mechanism and the decay properties of ^{18}B . The validity of the simulation was verified through various comparisons with experimental data and the only remaining free parameters are related to the decay energy. In the case of p - or d -waves the energy and width of a Breit–Wigner resonance were varied. For an s -wave decay the scattering length was varied. Apart from the decay of discrete unbound states which

Fig. 2. Decay energy spectrum of ^{16}B reconstructed from n - ^{15}B coincidences. The solid line is the best fit to the experimental spectrum comprising of a resonance at 60 ± 20 keV (dotted line) and a non-resonant contribution (dashed line) at 0.5 MeV. Inset: (a) ^{15}B level scheme from [39]. Measurements of the ^{16}B ground state (b) from Kalpakchieva et al. [38], (c) from Lecouey et al. [37], (d) results from the present work, (e) shell model calculations [37].

can be described with the s -, p - or d -waves lineshapes, the experimental spectra include reconstructed events which correspond to decay from the continuum. These create a non-resonant background under the discrete levels [36] which can be described by a Maxwellian distribution of beam velocity neutrons. In the simulations the peak energy of this distribution was varied in order to fit the experimental spectra. The height of the resonant and non-resonant components was scaled to obtain the best fit.

Using the same experimental setup and analysis procedure, the decay energy of ^{16}B from a single-proton removal from a ^{17}C beam was also investigated. The energy of the ^{17}C secondary beam was 55 MeV/u and the reaction of interest took place in a 470 mg/cm^2 Be target. This decay was recently studied by Lecouey et al. [37]. They used the same reaction and found a d -wave decay at 85 ± 15 keV, with a width of $\Gamma \ll 100$ keV width. The decay energy spectrum from the present work is shown in Fig. 2. A χ^2 analysis showed that the best fit of our decay energy spectrum corresponds to a Breit–Wigner line shape at a resonance energy of 60 ± 20 keV which is in agreement with the results of Ref. [37] and also with the earlier work by Kalpakchieva et al. [38] ($E = 40 \pm 40$ keV, $\Gamma < 100$ keV). The width of the distribution is dominated by the experimental resolution and the data are consistent with the very small width (0.5 keV) expected for the specific decay [37].

Fig. 3 shows the experimental spectrum for the ^{18}B decay. For comparison, the upper panel of Fig. 3 shows the acceptances of our setup plotted on the same energy axis as the ^{18}B decay spectrum. The experimental spectrum could not be fitted satisfactorily with a Breit–Wigner line shape. The best fit was obtained from an s -wave analysis of the resulting decay. The s -wave line shape was calculated according to the time dependent projectile fragmentation model of Blanchon et al. [40] taking the initial wave function of ^{19}C in a Wood–Saxon potential which was parameterized to fit the experimental binding energy. The best fit to the experimental data corresponds to a scattering length of -100 fm. A χ^2 analysis showed that we can only give an upper limit to the scattering length of this virtual state at -50 fm (1σ from minimum), while further reduction of the scattering length does not have a significant impact on the fit. The non-resonant contribution shown in

Fig. 3. Decay energy spectrum of ^{18}B reconstructed from n - ^{17}B coincidences. The solid line presents the best fit to the experimental spectrum and it consists of the s -wave line shape for scattering length of -100 fm (black short dash line) and a non-resonant background (black dash line). The corresponding grey lines show the two components without the effect of the resolutions and efficiency of our experimental setup. The acceptance distribution of our setup is shown in the upper panel on the same axis as the decay energy spectrum for comparison. The inset shows experimental and calculated level schemes of ^{17}B as well as shell model calculations for ^{18}B where the arrows show the most favored decay modes.

Fig. 3 corresponds to a Maxwellian distribution at 0.5 MeV. The s -wave results and the corresponding scattering length were not sensitive to the peak energy of the non-resonant component. Using the upper limit in the scattering length we can extract an upper limit for the energy as well. This is done using the relation $E \simeq \hbar^2/2\mu\alpha^2$ from Ref. [41], where α is the scattering length and μ is the reduced mass. The upper limit of -50 fm corresponds to a decay energy of 10 keV.

In the present experiment we populated states in ^{18}B through a single-proton knockout reaction from a ^{19}C beam. ^{19}C is considered to be a one-neutron halo nucleus. As mentioned earlier, its ground state configuration is believed to be $\nu(d_{5/2})^4\nu(s_{1/2})^1$. Although ^{19}C is a very neutron-rich nucleus, it is assumed here that the removal of a single proton at 60 MeV/u beam energy is a direct process during which the neutrons are largely undisturbed [42]. The removal of nucleons of the deficient species to study exotic nuclei has been used in several experiments (e.g. [43–45]). Based on this assumption, we expect in the present experiment to populate ^{18}B largely in the configuration $\pi(p_{3/2})^{-1} \otimes \nu(d_{5/2})^4\nu(s_{1/2})^1$. This configuration can couple to states with spin and parity of 1^- and 2^- . Once ^{18}B is created in the above configuration, it is expected to decay mainly through the emission of an s -wave neutron.

Shell model calculations were performed using the code NuShell@MSU [46]. The calculations used the WBP interaction [14] in the s - p - sd - pf model space. Table 1 presents the first 6 calculated levels of ^{18}B for which the energy above the ground state is shown in the first column and the spin and parity assignments in the second column. The spectroscopic factors C^2S for removing a $p_{3/2}$ proton from ^{19}C are listed in the third column for the cases where the C^2S was non-zero. Columns four and five show the spectroscopic overlaps between the different states in ^{18}B and

Table 1
Shell model calculations using the code NuShell@MSU with the WBP interaction in the s - p - sd - pf model space. Only the first six states in ^{18}B are presented.

E_x (MeV)	J^π	C^2S (^{19}C (g.s.)- ^{18}B)	Final state in ^{17}B	C^2S (mode) (^{18}B - ^{17}B)
0	2^-	1.56	g.s. ($\frac{3}{2}^-$)	0.51 ($s_{1/2}$) 0.01 ($d_{3/2}$) 0.06 ($d_{5/2}$)
0.498	4^-			
0.739	2^-	0.07	g.s. ($\frac{3}{2}^-$) 1459 ($\frac{5}{2}^-$)	0.05 ($s_{1/2}$) < 0.01 ($d_{3/2}$) 0.06 ($d_{5/2}$) 0.33 ($s_{1/2}$) < 0.01 ($d_{3/2}$) 0.09 ($d_{5/2}$)
0.973	3^-			
1.137	1^-	0.78	g.s. ($\frac{3}{2}^-$) 1459 ($\frac{5}{2}^-$)	0.46 ($s_{1/2}$) < 0.01 ($d_{3/2}$) 0.02 ($d_{5/2}$) < 0.01 ($s_{1/2}$) 0.38 ($d_{5/2}$)
1.912	1^-			

^{17}B for the energetically possible decays. According to these calculations, starting with a ^{19}C beam, the 2^- ground state and the 1^- excited state are preferentially populated in ^{18}B . The ground state of ^{18}B is expected to decay via an s -wave to the ground state of ^{17}B . The decay from the first 1^- state can proceed either through a d -wave neutron to the first excited state ($\frac{5}{2}^-$) of ^{17}B (if it is energetically possible), or through the emission of an s -wave neutron to the ground state of ^{17}B .

The inset of Fig. 3 shows the decay paths from the 2^- ground state and the 1^- excited state of ^{18}B . The calculations show that the 1^- state is lower in energy than the first $\frac{5}{2}^-$ excited state of ^{17}B and therefore this decay would not be possible. However, the experimental results from Kanungo et al. [47] and from Kondo et al. [48] show that the energy of the $\frac{5}{2}^-$ state is 1089(15) keV and 1070(10) keV, respectively. Thus, depending on the actual energy of the 1^- excited state in ^{18}B , decay from the 1^- state in ^{18}B to the first excited state in ^{17}B could be possible. From our results we cannot rule out the possibility that we populate such a bound excited state in ^{17}B . However, the s -wave line shape needed for describing the decay energy spectrum is a strong indication that the observed spectrum corresponds to the decay of the ground state of ^{18}B . The calculations show that the spectroscopic overlap between the 1^- excited state of ^{18}B with the ground state of ^{17}B is similar to the one with the first excited state of ^{17}B . As shown in the inset of Fig. 3 these two decays are expected to be different by at least 1 MeV. Although the efficiency of our experimental setup is lower for higher decay energies, the fact that no structure is emerging from the background in the region around 1 MeV indicates that there is no significant contribution from the decay of the 1^- state to the low decay energies.

Our results provide an additional experimental verification of the s -wave configuration of the ground state of ^{19}C . In the case of a d -wave configuration for ^{19}C , we would populate ^{18}B in a configuration corresponding to the coupling of $\nu(d_{5/2}) \otimes \pi(p_{3/2})$. The four possible J^π states, i.e. 1^- , 2^- , 3^- and 4^- , would all be expected to decay via a d -wave which is not consistent with our experimental results.

As mentioned earlier the evolution of the sd shell for the $N = 13$ isotones lowers the $s_{1/2}$ orbital in energy with respect to

the $d_{5/2}$ orbital as the number of protons is reduced. This evolution results in a mixing between the two orbitals for ^{19}C and could lead to an inversion for nuclei with even fewer protons. ^{18}B has one less proton than ^{19}C and is therefore the first candidate for the inversion between the $s_{1/2}$ and $d_{5/2}$ orbitals. We investigate here whether our experimental result is consistent with such an sd inversion. In the case where the $s_{1/2}$ orbital is much lower than the $d_{5/2}$ orbital one could naively assume a pure $(s_{1/2})^2 \otimes (d_{5/2})^3$ configuration. In this case the ground state of ^{18}B would decay via a d -wave. If the strong mixture of the two orbitals from ^{19}C persists to ^{18}B as well, one would expect a dominant s -wave decay. The experimental results from the present work are consistent with the latter case, since the decay energy spectrum was best fitted with an s -wave line shape.

The observation of an s -wave alone is not evidence that the measured decay is coming from the ground state of ^{18}B . However, the present result gives an upper limit of 10 keV in the decay energy which is rather low. If the observed decay corresponded to an excited state of ^{18}B , then one would expect the ground state to be bound. ^{18}B is known to be unbound with respect to neutron emission, therefore we propose that the observed s -wave corresponds to the decay of the ground state of ^{18}B .

A virtual ground state in ^{18}B also supports the possibility of the presence of Efimov states in ^{19}B according to Muzumdar et al. [9]. The same reference reports that Efimov states would be expected in ^{19}B only if the virtual ground state of ^{18}B would correspond to a scattering length of a few hundred fm. The result of the present work, which yields an upper limit of -50 fm, is consistent with the aforementioned criteria, although it does not allow a decisive conclusion.

In conclusion, we populated ^{18}B through a single proton knock-out reaction from a ^{19}C beam. The decay energy spectrum was reconstructed event-by-event from four momentum vectors of the decay products ^{17}B and neutron. The best fit to the decay energy spectrum came from an s -wave line shape. An upper limit for the scattering length was found to be -50 fm, which corresponds to an energy < 10 keV. This result is a strong indication that the $s_{1/2}$ - $d_{5/2}$ mixing observed in the ground state of ^{19}C persists in the first unbound $N = 13$ isotope.

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